

DALIA,

Use Cases and User Stories

DALIA Team

Contents

Motivation	2
Use Case 01: Search Tool for Best Practice Guides	3
Use Case 02: Search Tool for Evaluation of Data Quality	5
Use Case 03: Publishing Metadata via the Knowledge Base	7
Use Case 04: Suggestions for a Learning Path	8
Use Case 05: Suggestions for Competences	9
Use Case 06: Suggestions for Topics	10
Use Case 07: Searching and Sorting Topics	11
Use Case 08: Feedback and Report	13
Use Case 09: Content Update Notifications	14
Bibliography	15

Motivation

In today's digital society, the ability to handle, understand, and manage data in an efficient way is increasingly recognized as a fundamental skill across all disciplines. The DALIA project (DAta LIteracy Alliance¹) aims to foster data literacy by providing high-quality, openly accessible educational resources (OER). These materials are designed to meet the diverse needs of learners and professionals at various educational levels, levels of RDM experience, and disciplinary backgrounds. The resources are contributed by a wide range of institutions, including the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortia, national Research Data Management (RDM) initiatives, data competence centers, and other stakeholders from the research and education landscape. To enable efficient access and use of these learning materials, DALIA is developing a knowledge graph that supports semantic linking and integration, adhering to the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable^{2,3}.

A central element of the DALIA platform development is the implementation of an agile, user-centred approach. Core to this methodology are user stories, which articulate specific user needs and expectations in a structured, scenario-based format⁴. Each user story is framed as: “As a [role with specific RDM experience], I have the [need/requirement] to be fulfilled by a [knowledge base function].” This format ensures that requirements are clearly linked to both the user context and the intended system functionality, while maintaining cross-disciplinary applicability.

Based on these user stories, more detailed use cases are developed, specifying triggers, user actions, system responses, expected outcomes, and acceptance criteria. These use cases guide the iterative design and development of the platform and ensure alignment with real-world needs. The user stories encompass both, the perspectives of learners—seeking relevant learning materials—and contributors, who wish to publish content, share feedback, or access usage reports.

The initial set of user stories was developed by combining general community input and a structured community workshop. Participants were invited to describe their needs via a targeted survey, considering their role, educational level, specialization, and intended use of the platform. This participatory process enabled the integration of a wide range of perspectives and ensured that the platform supports diverse usage scenarios. Through continuous refinement of user stories and active community involvement, DALIA remains adaptive, inclusive, and responsive to evolving user needs in the field of research data management and data literacy.

Use Case 01: Search Tool for Best Practice Guides

Research generates data. To maximize the utility of this data and ensure its long-term sustainability and accessibility, researchers aim to store and manage it according to the FAIR principles. To address this challenge, high-quality, easy-to-understand guides are essential for helping researchers streamline the data management process. The DALIA knowledge graph serves as a central resource for information on research data management, offering structured guidelines and best practices. A search tool based on the knowledge graph enables researchers to specifically search for relevant content, tailored to their data management needs.

Trigger

A researcher has data from measurements or simulations and wants to store it in a way that follows FAIR principles.

Actions

- The researcher visits the DALIA portal.
Optional: *If logged in, researcher gets more personalised recommendations.*
- The researcher inputs a query, such as, “Store Data FAIRly”
- The search tool processes the query and provides a list of results, which are linked to relevant guidelines from the knowledge base that match the researcher’s discipline (if provided), data type, and context.
Optional: *The researcher refines the search results using the filter options, e.g. by selecting the researcher’s discipline.*
- The researcher reviews and selects an appropriate guideline from the list.
- The researcher views the respective guideline and follows the steps outlined.
Optional: *The researcher may receive a follow-up from DALIA asking whether the guideline was helpful to further improve future search results.*

Expected Results

- The researcher finds a set of best-practice guidelines accepted by domain experts.
- The researcher is confident that the selected guideline is up-to-date, accurate, and validated by experts.
- The researcher successfully stores their measurement or simulation data according to the FAIR principles.

Acceptance Criteria

- The search tool is easy to use as it allows the researcher to input queries using relevant search terms. How is ease of use measured? e.g., Number of clicks to find relevant content? DALIA provides relevant results that match the needs of the researcher's query.
- The quality of the guideline is ensured through the curation process.

Use Case 02: Search Tool for Evaluation of Data Quality

Researching with data from external sources requires a clear understanding and assessment of the quality as well as accuracy, completeness, and consistency of the data. For this purpose, researchers need accessible criteria, metrics and tools for evaluating data quality. It is especially desirable if there are tools that can automatically or semi-automatically assess the quality of the data according to a standard, helping researchers to quickly determine whether the data meets their needs. In addition, the platform provides a section with reviews, where users rate their experience with the resources.

Trigger

A researcher wants to evaluate the quality of data from an external source or another research project using available metrics and tools.

Actions

- The researcher visits the DALIA portal.
Optional: If logged in, researcher gets more personalised recommendations
- The researcher enters specific search terms to query criteria, metrics and tools for evaluating data quality, such as “assess data quality”.
- The search tool provides a list of relevant materials from the knowledge base (including metric standards, and tools)
Optional: The researcher refines the search results using the filter options, e.g. by selecting the researcher’s discipline.
- The researcher selects suitable material.
- The researcher is referenced to the tools source, including (optional) download, documentation and contact to the maintainer.

Expected Results

- The researcher finds domain-specific, established metrics and tools for data quality assessment.
- The researcher can quickly access and find metrics and tools without spending excessive time.

Acceptance Criteria

- Established, domain-specific metrics and tools for different disciplines are available.
- Detailed documentations on how to apply metrics and tools across different data sets and domains are provided.

Use Case 03: Publishing Metadata via the Knowledge Base

Researchers often develop Research Data Management tools (e.g., software applications) to automate or simplify their workflows. Sharing these tools can benefit others in the research community. The DALIA Knowledge Base aims to enhance the visibility and accessibility of tools and their documentation. As the tools are listed in DALIA via their metadata and are easily accessible via a “Go to Resource” function.

Trigger

A researcher wishes to publish the metadata of Research Data Management tools from their research to the Knowledge Base to make the tools more findable, share valuable resources with other researchers, and enhance collaboration.

Actions

- The researcher visits the DALIA portal.
- The researcher logs in.
- The researcher clicks the “Add Resource” button on the user profile page.
- The researcher provides mandatory metadata for the publishing, like the link to the repository where the tool is published. To improve findability, optional metadata can also be included.
- If the researcher needs assistance with the publishing, they can click the help link available on the page.

Expected Results

- The researcher can easily use the “Add Resource” functionality.
- The researcher can use picklists to specify metadata for publishing.

Acceptance Criteria

- The “Add Resource” functionality is simple and intuitive.
- The instructions for using the “Add Resource” functionality are clear and easy to understand.
- The metadata schema is transparent and well-documented.

Use Case 04: Suggestions for a Learning Path

Instructors upload metadata to educational materials to the DALIA portal. To help students systematically navigate the learning materials and possess the necessary prerequisite knowledge, instructors typically want to suggest a learning path.

Trigger

After an instructor uploads sufficient metadata to learning resources stored in suitable repositories or selects already existing resources in DALIA, a learning path is automatically generated based on this metadata. The instructor can modify the automatically generated learning path according to their needs and provide the resulting collection/learning path via link.

Actions

- The instructor logs in and uploads all relevant metadata to materials or selects desired metadata sets already registered in DALIA.
- The knowledge base suggests a learning path based on the materials' metadata. The instructor can either accept the suggestion or make modifications.
- The instructor shares the learning path with the students by a link.
- The students follow the learning path.

Expected Results

- The instructor can create the learning path without investing excessive time.
- The learning path can be easily shared.
- Both the instructor and the students have a clear overview of the learning path.
- Instructors and students benefit from an efficient and effective learning environment.

Acceptance Criteria

- DALIA allows the creation and sharing of customised learning paths.
- Instructors can easily modify existing learning paths.
- Students can resume a learning path they started at any time.
- The functionalities are intuitive, facilitating use for both instructors and students.

Use Case 05: Suggestions for Competences

Training materials for research data management, essential for various professional competencies, are made available through the DALIA knowledge base. Registered learners in DALIA should receive suggestions for learning paths that are critical for their professional skills. The knowledge base contains structured learning paths across different subjects and disciplines, covering the necessary steps for competency development.

Trigger

Registered learners see suggestions for competencies and corresponding learning paths on their profile.

Actions

- The learner logs into the DALIA platform and visits their profile.
- The knowledge base recommends one or more learning paths based on the learner's discipline and activities.
- The learner selects a learning path that aligns with their interests.
- The learner follows the suggested learning path and completes the various learning units.

Expected Results

- The learner receives valuable suggestions for learning paths.
- DALIA provides reliable and relevant recommendations based on the users' profession and their competency levels.

Acceptance Criteria

- The suggested learning paths cover all necessary steps for developing the desired competencies.
- The quality of the proposed learning paths is high.
- The learner can apply the knowledge gained in their professional field after completion.

Use Case 06: Suggestions for Topics

After learners have engaged with a topic, they often wish to explore additional relevant topics. These topics may relate to prerequisite knowledge or fall within the same subject or domain. The goal is to provide a personalised learning experience.

Trigger

Relevant topics are suggested to learners when they view a resource or users' profile.

Actions

- The learner logs into the DALIA platform and selects a specific topic to study.
- The knowledge base suggests one or more topics based on the learner's competency level, discipline, and activity.
- The learner engages with the suggested topics.

Expected Results

- The learner receives useful suggestions about new topics.
- The suggested topics align with the learner's competency level, discipline, and activity.
- DALIA provides reliable and valuable suggestions.

Acceptance Criteria

- The suggested topics are relevant and based on the learner's behavior.
- The suggestions offer a suitable variety, allowing the learner to choose from multiple options.
- DALIA facilitates smooth navigation to the suggested topics.

Use Case 07: Searching and Sorting Topics

Data science has emerged as a valuable skill across various industries, and developing Data Science skills can open up new career opportunities or enhance professional job skills. However, balancing a busy schedule with work, study, and other commitments requires efficient ways to find high-quality, practical courses.

Trigger

A learner seeking to build or expand data science skills searches for relevant online courses on the DALIA platform to improve career opportunities or enhance current job skills.

Actions

- The learner logs into the DALIA platform.
- The learner uses the search functionality, applying filters to specify the type of course they are looking for, such as “Target Group”, “Language”, “Learning Resource Type”.
- The learner uses the keyword “AND” between search terms in the search bar to ensure all search terms must appear in the search results.
- The platform displays a list of relevant courses, which can be filtered and arranged based on filters.
- The learner selects a course that meets their criteria, enrolls, and begins learning.

Expected Results

- Ability to search for specific terms that must appear within the description of the documents.
- Courses can be quickly assessed and compared using detailed metadata and content, aiding in the selection of the most appropriate option.
- The selected course provides practical, hands-on knowledge that can be applied immediately to current work or used to enhance career-related skills.

Acceptance Criteria

- The platform allows the use of “AND” keyword to combine search terms.
- Filters are available and user-friendly.
- Courses are practically oriented, providing hands-on knowledge, and not overly theoretical, catering to the needs of a demanding learner.
- Courses can be quickly identified based on clear descriptions and metadata, making the selection process efficient.

Use Case 08: Feedback and Report

In the DALIA platform, learners can access a wide range of educational materials. To ensure a positive learning experience, learners should be able to report inappropriate content or rule violations. This feature allows learners to provide feedback on the quality of the content and the adherence to guidelines. By marking inappropriate content, learners can help maintain a respectful and safe learning environment.

Trigger

A learner encounters content that is inappropriate, offensive, or violates the platform's guidelines. The learner wishes to report the content to the platform administrators for review and appropriate action.

Actions

- The learner logs into the DALIA platform.
- The learner navigates to the content they wish to report.
- The learner selects the option to report the content.
- The platform provides a form where the learner can specify the reason for the report and provide additional comments if necessary.
- The learner submits the report.
- The platform processes the report and takes appropriate action, such as removing the content, issuing a warning, or contacting the content creator.

Expected Outcomes

- Learners can report inappropriate content or rule violations to maintain a positive learning environment.
- The platform administrators can review reported content and take appropriate action.
- The reporting feature helps ensure the quality and integrity of the educational materials available on the platform.

Acceptance Criteria

- The platform provides a clear and easily accessible option to report content.
- Learners can specify the reason for the report and provide additional comments.
- The reporting process is transparent, and learners receive feedback on the outcome of their report.

Use Case 09: Content Update Notifications

In the DALIA platform, learners have access to a wide range of educational resources and materials. To ensure that learners have the most up-to-date information and content, it is essential to provide notifications when new or updated files are available. Learners may have specific topics, resources, or categories that they are interested in and would like to be notified when new content is added or existing content is updated. This feature helps learners stay informed and engaged with the latest educational materials.

Trigger

A learner is interested in specific topics, resources, or categories available on the DALIA platform and wants to receive notifications when new or updated files are available for the topics, resources, or categories they are interested in or existing content is updated.-

Actions

- The learner logs into the DALIA platform.
- The learner navigates to the topics, resources, or categories they are interested in.
- The learner subscribes to specific topics, resources, or categories to receive notifications.
- The learner selects their preferred notification method (e.g., email, in-app notifications).
- When new or updated files are available for the subscribed topics, resources, or categories, the learner receives a notification.

Expected Outcomes

- Learners receive timely notifications when new or updated files are available for the topics, resources, or categories they are interested in.
- Learners can stay informed and up-to-date with the latest educational materials.

Acceptance Criteria

- Learners can easily subscribe to specific topics, resources, or categories to receive notifications.
- The notification system is reliable and delivers notifications in a timely manner.
- Learners can choose their preferred notification method.

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